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Estimating sources of noise to Network of Nigerian Seismic Stations

By

Kadiri Umar Afegbua
F.O. Ezomo

Research Article

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^{1*}Kadiri Umar Afegbua and ²F.O. Ezomo

^{1*}Earthquake Seismology Dept., Centre for Geodesy and Geodynamics, P.M.B. 11, Toro, Bauchi State, Nigeria.

²Department of Physics, Faculty of Physical Sciences, University of Benin Ugbowo, Benin City, Edo State, Nigeria.

Corresponding Author's Email: umakad@yahoo.com, Tel: +2348037122784.

ABSTRACT

Estimation of possible sources of noise to the (Kaduna, Toro, Nsukka, Ife, Awka) operational seismographic stations (Kaduna, Toro, Nsukka, Ife and Awka) in Nigeria, has been carried out using recommended distances by Wilmore (1979) and physical observations through field work. The results showed more contributions of anthropogenic noise, less ambient and instrumentation noise. Human activities around the five stations including vehicular traffic, contribute significant cultural noise to the stations. In addition, noise other sources like trees, streams, ocean, and storms and other forms of ambient noise especially in the southern part of Nigeria were observed. Instrumental malfunctioning in some stations like Toro; the geologic nature of the site like the Nsukka station as well as the siting procedures of some stations like the Kaduna where a 16 sec sensor is installed on the surface without vault are likely responsible for the observed high noise. Since no noise analysis was carried out before the siting of the stations, this paper was intended to identify sources of noise and recommend better practices for establishing future seismic stations in Nigeria and environ, for improved data quality.

Keywords: NNNSS, noise and sources, Wilmore's recommended distances, field observations.

INTRODUCTION

Conventionally, noise is a disturbance in the signal which does not represent part of a message from a specified source (Sherriff, 1991). Noise is unwanted sound and it is one prominent source of data quality worsening (Alguacil and Havskov, 2002). Sources of noise include Vocal cord, a running engine, a vibrating loudspeaker diaphragm, an operating machine tool, and so on.

Basically, the origin of noise is from instrumentation and real seismic noise from the earth vibrations. However, the instrumental noise is normally well below the noise from actual earth vibrations (Alguacil and Havskov, 2002). But this is often difficult to see unless one is familiar with the characteristics of the noise at a particular station under consideration. Nonetheless, most sensors (e.g. an accelerometer at low frequencies) will exhibit some frequency band where the instrumental noise is dominating (Alguacil and Havskov, 2002).

On the other hand, ambient vibrations or ambient noise are generated from various types of vibration sources. These vibrations are mostly surface waves (Rayleigh waves, Love waves) propagating on the surface (Alguacil and Havskov, 2002; Encyclopedia). Low frequency waves (below 1 Hz) are generally called microseisms and high frequency waves (above 1 Hz) are called microtremors (Havskov and Ottemoller, 2008).

Noise are either natural (e.g. tides, water waves striking the coast, turbulent wind, effects of wind on trees or buildings, Volcanic tremor, geologic noise...) or cultural (e.g. traffic, rotating or hammering machinery, human base noise etc). Natural noise is subdivided into Microtremors and Microseisms. While microtremors are mainly cultural from the actions of human beings e.g. traffic and machinery, microseismic noise with shorter frequencies are ocean generated noise; mostly widespread and present less prominent in the interior of continents than the coastal regions (Alguacil and Havskov, 2002). Other sources of noise to seismic stations are rain, traffic, wind, industrial noise in the urban areas. Man made noise and wind noise are usually the main sources at high frequencies and since the lower limit is about 0.01 nm at 10 Hz, very small disturbances will quickly get the noise level above this value (Alguacil and Havskov, 2002).

Other sources of noise to seismic stations are noise from instrumental tilt that is very visible on the horizontal component of a sensor; thermal electronic noise; quantization noise; barometric noise; Brownian noise; Coda noise; instrumental self-noise and electrical (electronic) noise.

Figure 1: Vertical component of noise traces in order of top to bottom, from **Ife, Toro, Kaduna, Nsukka** and **Awka** stations respectively (from PQL II software).

There are many types of noise for land data, most of which are viewed as unwanted signal—repeatable, deterministic phenomena that we physically understand but don't want in our data, such as multiples, source-generated noise (e.g., ground roll) (Alguacil and Havskov, 2002). Other noise types might be better modeled as a random process (e.g., wind noise). Most or many of these effects are removed or reduced in extensive processing (Brodhead, 2008). In essence, all recorded seismic signals (whether from seismometers or geophones) always contain noise and what is important to users of such data, is how to establish both the source(s) of the noise and how to measure its level (Havscov and Ottemoller, 2008), which is the focus of this research.

Nigerian Network of Seismograph Stations

Before 1960, there were generally only individual seismic stations operating independently. But today, several stations are operating in a country or region, to make up a network, like the Nigerian national Network of Seismograph Stations (NNNSS) (NMSOP, Chap. 8). The three main purposes of seismic networks are for seismic alarm, or general or specific seismic monitoring, and research on the interior of the Earth (Alguacil & Havskov, 2002). However, the most basic goal is the determination of accurate earthquake locations. The first phase of Nigeria's network comprises of five stations (Figure 1; Table 1), while the second and third phases is expected to increase the number of stations to ten and fifteen respectively. Local, regional and global research into the Earth's interior is the oldest goal of seismology, and quality data are required with less noise to achieve this. Seismic networks are and probably will be forever the only tool that enables study of the detailed structure and physical properties of the deeper Earth's interior. (NMSOP, Chap. 8). The observance of noise on the seismic data from the Nigerian Network is affecting the quality of the data for precise earthquakes location and meaningful research activities. This study therefore, is intended to identify possible sources of noise to the seismic stations in Nigeria and proffer better practices to locate future seismic networks away from various sources of noise to generate data suitable for reliable research. It is difficult if not impossible, to completely exclude noise from a seismic trace; however, it is highly recommended to relocate an intolerably noisy station to another site where high signal to noise ratio would be enhanced.

Table 1: Location of Centre for Geodesy and Geodynamics Seismological Stations

S/N	Station Name	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation (m)	Geologic Foundation	Instrumentation (From Entec manufacturers).
1	Oyo	07°53.131'N	03°57.078'E	295	Gneiss	Seismograph: DR4000 recorder Seismometer: EP105 broadband seismometer
2	Ibadan	07°27.251'N	03°53.520'E	193	Gneiss	
3	Ile-Ife	07°32.800'N	04°32.815'E	289	Gneiss	Seismograph: DR4000 recorder Seismometer: EP105 broadband seismometer
4	Awka	06°14.561'N	07°06.693'E	50	Shale and siltstone	Seismograph: DR4000 recorder Seismometer: SP400 medium period seismometer
5	Nsukka	06°52.011'N	07°25.045'E	430	Sandstone	Seismograph: DR4000 recorder Seismometer: EP105 broadband seismometer
6	Abakiliki	06°23.453'N	08°01.474'E	82	Sandstone	No instrument installed
7	Abuja	08°59.126'N	07°23.380'E	432	Gneiss	No instrument installed
8	Toro (Central)	10°03.303'N	09°07.089'E	882	Gneiss	No instrument installed
9	Kaduna	10°26.101'N	07°38.484'E	668	Gneiss	Seismograph: DR4000 recorder Seismometer: SP400 medium period
10	Minna	09°30.702'N	06°26.411'E	203	Granite	No instrument installed

The Centre for Geodesy and Geodynamics (CGG) has been operating the Nigerian National Network of Seismographic Stations (NNNSS) located in triangulations (Figure 1) across Nigeria since 2006. The properties of the respective stations are shown in table 1, modified after Afegbua et al. (2011). Other information regarding the equipment at the respective stations are shown in table 2. The Awka, Kaduna, Nsukka, Ife and Toro are currently operational while installation of equipment at Abakiliki, Oyo, Minna, Abuja, Ibadan stations would be completed soon. The sensors at Nsukka, Awka and Ife are placed inside a vault of about 6m deep in University communities with surrounding residential buildings, while the sensors at Kaduna and Toro stations are placed on the surface of a basement in relatively quiet environments and are about 100 m - 600 m distances from vehicular traffic, human activities and some surrounding trees and few residential houses. While stations located in the southern part of Nigeria are few kilometers away from the Atlantic Ocean and some fast running streams with surrounding human settlements, others are located far away in the north with sparsely populated settlements, no streams apart from surrounding trees. The findings from this work are also to assist engineers and operators of seismic stations in better site selection to minimize noise.

Figure 2: Map of Nigeria showing locations of existing and planned stations (courtesy Afegbua et al., 2011).

The main purpose for collecting data on seismic background noise, amongst others, is for assessing the suitability of sites for temporary or permanent seismic recordings. Prior to the construction of the five Nigerian National Network of Seismographic Stations (NNNSS) currently operational (Figure 1), no noise analysis was carried out to ascertain the sites' noise characteristics and possibly identifying the sources of the noise. Since 2008 when the stations started generating data till date, no attempt whatsoever, had been made to investigate the noise level inherent in the useful data or to ascertain the noise sources. As a result, it is suspected that the quality of the data from these stations has been impaired. In selecting quality site for seismic stations and seismic equipment, the task of seismic observations and their resolution, dynamic range, bandwidth and frequency range are paramount (Bormann, 1998). Till now noise data are collected with a wide range of instruments, both analog and digital, of different bandwidth, resolution and transfer functions.

NNNSS are installed with the broadband sensors which are very popular choice today because they provide complete seismic information from about 0.01 Hz to 50 Hz and therefore allow a much broader range of studies than the Short Period (SP) records, as in the case of geophones (NMSOP, Chap. 8). They also require very careful site selection in a seismological-geological sense, a better-controlled environment in seismic vaults, and they are sometimes a bit tricky to install. Since they do not attenuate at the 0.12 - 0.3 Hz natural seismic noise peak, their raw output signal contains much more seismic noise than signals from a Short Period seismometer (NMSOP, Chap. 8). Consequently, useful seismic signals are often buried in seismic noise and can be resolved and analyzed only after filtering to remove the background noise, as currently experienced with data from NNNSS. So, for all events apart from the largest earthquakes, filtering is required even for making simple phase picks. Filtering has its disadvantages which include, change in the phase which can have serious implications when reading arrival times of seismic phases; contamination of data phase shifts due to digitizer anti aliasing filters and it causes energy to move backwards in the signal and there will be a phase shift and so on (Alguacil and Havskov, 2002).

Figure 3: An hour-long window of unfiltered seismic traces (Z, N, E, components from up to down) from Kaduna Station. The Z component trace is obscured by noise.

Figure 4: An hour-long window of filtered seismic traces (Z, N, E, components from up to down) band-pass filtered with 0.01-0.1Hz from Kaduna Station.

Figure 5: An hour-long window of filtered seismic traces (Z, N, E, components from up to down) with 1-5Hz filter band from Kaduna Station.

Figures 3-5 demonstrate typical challenges encountered during routine processing data from NNNSS. It can be seen clearly that the vertical component (upper trace) of Figure 3 is completely shrouded with noise which makes picking seismic phases impossible except filters are applied with its attendant effects. Even after applying 0.01-0.1Hz (High-pass) filters, figure 4 does not give a clear primary phase arrival position or time, as it remains hidden in the noise on the Z-component and not distinct on both the N (middle trace) and E (lower trace) components respectively. Application of 1-5Hz filters worsened the traces as shown in figure 5, meaning, it is a distant indistinct event.

To mitigate these obstacles that cause data deterioration, it is worthwhile to ascertain all possible sources of noise to seismic before they are constructed at a particular site. For NNNSS and other networks, this study should assist operators of seismic stations to adopt better practices aimed at reducing observed noise on their data, with a view to constructing vaults, acquisition of longer period sensors depending on the purposes they are purchased for, proper insulation of the sensor etc.

Results from Field Work And Minimal Distances Estimation Of Seismic Sources

Minimum recommended noise-source-to-station-site distances according to Wilmore (1979) and actual distances (Trnkoczy, 1999) for the seismic station of Kaduna are represented in table 2. The same estimation was done for the five stations (Ife, Nsukka, Kaduna, Toro, Awka) using Wilmore (1979), but for space constraints, all the tables are not provided here. However, the summaries of the findings that are not too different from one station to the other are contained in this work (See Discussion).

In relationship, Wilmore (1979) method had been used to estimate actual distances of sources of noise to seismic stations in Greenland, a European station on bedrock in a populated area 15 km away from heavy traffic, and in Japan, etc (NMSOP, Chap. 7). During the field work, table 2 without the values as shown in the actual

distance column was distributed to local people living around the stations, to obtain comprehensive questionnaire feedbacks, in addition to physical visitations by a team of geoscientists and engineers to all the stations. The findings are summarized in the discussion below.

Table 2: Estimated actual distances of sources of noise to Kaduna station (Wilmore, 1979). In adopting Wilmore (1979) in this work, it was based on the premise that the Source and seismometer of the respective stations are on the same geological formation and with no intervening alluvial valley or mountain range.

STATION SITE NAME:e.g.--- <u>KADUNA STATION</u>		SITE #: <u> 2 </u>			DATE OF ANALYSIS: <u> 06 /10 /2012 </u>			Actual Distance	
COORDINATES: N <u> 10 </u> <u> 0 </u> <u> 26' </u> <u> 00.86" </u> S W <u> 7 </u> <u> 0 </u> <u> 38' </u> <u> -26.29" </u> E		HARD MASSIVE ROCK, GRANITE, QUARTZITE, ETC.			HARDPAN HARD CLAY, ETC				
		RECOMMENDED MINIMAL DISTANCES [km]							
		A	B	C	A	B	C	[km]	
1	Oceans, with coastal mountains system	300	50	1	300	50	1		
2	Oceans, with broad coastal plains	1000	200	10	1000	200	20	1000KM	
3	Inland seas, bays, very large lakes, with coastal mountain system	150	25	1	150	25	1		
4	Inland seas, bays, very large lakes, with broad coastal plains	500	100	5	500	100	5	500KM	
5	Large dams, high waterfalls, large a cataracts	a	40	10	1	50	15	5	
		b	60	15	5	150	25	10	
6	Large oil or gas pipelines	a	20	10	5	30	15	5	
		b	100	30	10	100	30	10	30KM
7	Small lakes	a	20	10	1	20	10	1	
		b	50	15	1	50	15	1	
8	Heavy reciprocating machinery, a machinery	a	15	3	1	20	5	2	
		b	25	5	2	40	15	3	<5KM
9	Low waterfalls, rapids of a large river, intermittent flow over large dams	a	5	2	0.5	15	5	1	
		b	15	3	1	25	8	2	<3KM
10	Railway, frequent operation	a	6	3	1	10	5	1	
		b	15	5	1	20	10	1	<5KM
11	Airport, air ways heavy traffic	a	6	3	1	6	3	1	
		b							<10KM
12	Non-reciprocating power plant a machinery, balanced industrial machinery	a	2	0.5	0.1	10	4	1	
		b	4	1	0.2	15	6	1	.2KM

Table 2 Continues

13	Busy highway, mechanized farms	a							
		b	1	0.3	0.1	6	1	0.5	<3KM
14	Country roads, high buildings	a	0.3	0.2	0.05	2	1	0.5	
		b							<2KM
15	Low buildings, high trees and masts	a							
		b	0.1	0.03	0.01	0.3	0.1	0.05	<0.2KM
16	High fences, low trees, high bushes, large rocks	a							
		b	0.05	0.03	5m	0.06	0.03	0.01	<1KM

DISCUSSION

In figure 1, Nsukka station exhibited worst noise while Toro has less noise. Geologically, Nsukka is located on loose sediments while Toro station is located on a hard and immobile rock. Awka, Ife and Kaduna also exhibited remarkable high noise levels (Figure 1).

At Kaduna Station located in the northern part of Nigeria, the study showed less contributions of noise from Oceans, Inland seas, Bays, very large Lakes, High waterfalls, while large oil pipeline, heavy reciprocating machinery, low waterfalls, railways, industrial machinery, high buildings and fences, low trees, large rocks and high bushes are major sources of seismic noise.

Toro station, also located in the northern part of Nigeria exhibits similar noise sources. In addition, vehicular traffic and human activities close to the station contribute to the observed cultural noise despite its location on an immobile rock.

For Nsukka, Ife and Awka stations located in the southern part of Nigeria, the study showed significant contribution of noise from Oceans, High waterfalls, in addition to large oil pipeline, heavy reciprocating machinery, low waterfalls, industrial machinery, high buildings and fences, low trees, human activities and high bushes to the stations.

CONCLUSION

Wilmore (1979) recommended minimum distances (Trnkoczy, 1999) of seismic sources to seismograph stations was adopted to estimate possible sources of seismic noise to stations; Ife, Nsukka, Kaduna, Awka and Toro that form the first phase of the NNNSS. The distances of the sources were ascertained through physical visitations to the respective sites and the summarized information obtained from questionnaires circulated to local people around the stations. Significant noise sources observed are those contributing to anthropogenic noise in all the stations, while in addition to this, other sources contribute ambient noise from actual vibrations of the earth to the stations in the southern part of Nigeria more than in the north. Instrumental malfunctioning in some stations like Toro, the geologic nature of the site like the Nsukka station as well as the siting procedures of some stations like the Kaduna that is placed on the surface without vault and with a low period sensor of 16seconds, are likely responsible for the observed noise.

Geophysical exploration is usually conducted to locate significant accumulations of mineral deposits, clay deposit, oil, natural gas and other minerals, including ground water which are of economic importance to Nigeria as a nation in particular and the world in general. In the same vein, Groundwater exploration aids the general economy by prospecting and locating shallow aquifer that will never dry up (Ezomo and Akujieze, 2011a; 2011b). With enhanced data quality from NNNSS, it is possible to use seismological data for geophysical exploration as well.

Therefore, it is highly recommended that future seismic stations should be located away from these sources to minimize noise introduced on the data from human activities. It is also of optimal importance to operators of seismic stations to always know where and where not to construct a vault for seismic equipment and ensure proper functioning of installed instruments with respect to calibration and better insulation to check self-noise or instrumental noise that also manifest in the data.

Controlling environmental conditions for adequate shelter for seismic equipment should include: prevention of large temperature fluctuations in the equipment due to day/night temperature differences or because of weather

changes; prevention of large temperature fluctuations in the construction elements of the vault, resulting in seismometer tilt; ensuring adequate lightning protection; mitigation of electromagnetic interference (EMI); prevention of water damage to seismic equipment using vault drainage; prevention of dust and dirt from entering the shelter; and prevention of small animals from entering the shelter (NMSOP, Chap. 7).

It is equally recommended that seismic stations be fenced to minimize seismic noise caused by human activities or by animals that graze too close to the vault. It also contributes to the security of the station. Good contact between seismic sensors and bedrock is a basic requirement for quality stations, as soil and/or weathered rock layers between the sensor and the bedrock will modify seismic amplitudes and waveforms (NMSOP, Chap. 7).

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